

The Study Of Drinking Coffee Behavior And The Strategy Of 7s In Term Of Designing The Coffee Shop In The Education Institution In The Case Study Of Burapa University, Thailand

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Abstract

In Thailand, the market of the fresh coffee can be grown more comparing to the developed countries. The study was carried out to investigate the drinking coffee behavior of the consumers in the education institute and to study the coffee design as the 7Ps marketing strategies. This study utilized a quantitative research by collecting the data from the 400 samples (an estimated study population of 44,355) with the convenience sampling. They were consisted of the group of the administrators, the lecturers, the staffs and the students. The overall reliability (Cronbach's alpha) coefficient of the questionnaire was 0.972 In order to investigate the research objective, the descriptive statistics was used. The research finding showed that most customer were women (75.8%), their coffee drinking behavior can be described that Amazon coffee shop was their most favorite brand (46.3%), cold Latte coffee was their most favorite menu (26%), the convenience shop was the most reason why they concerned for using the service (31.4%). In the issue of finding of studying the coffee design as the 7Ps marketing strategies found that Pink is the most favorite color for decorating the shop (40.8%), using the ASEAN country furniture for decorating the shop was the most favorite (87%), the waitress outfit with the ASEAN style was the most favorite (77.8%), and decorating with the hard cover of the traditional ASEAN country books (96%). In conclusion, creating the differential from other coffee shops in the education institution may be the advantage of having the franchise business.

Introduction

Coffee market is currently experiencing considerable growth in economies around the world. It is one of the world's favorite beverages and a major source of caffeine for many students and employees, and coffee continues to be an integral factor in society's daily routine. It is also considered to be the second most sought-after commodity in the entire world, with worth over \$100 billion across the globe (Menke, 2018).

Globally there are 40,000 professional baristas according to coffee research specialists, and taking the job seriously also brings financial rewards (Hotson, 2015).

The business of catering to coffee drinkers in Thailand is booming, with an annual market estimated at 36 billion baht and rising, and the premium coffee segment will double in size, while the mass coffee market will grow by 2-3 times. Nevertheless, the number of the coffee drinker in Thailand was 300 cups a year in 2019 while the coffee lover in Japan and Europe were 400 cups and 600 cups respectively. Wake up and sell the coffee (bangkokpost.com). From this finding found that there is more room for Thailand to grow in the coffee industry. While most paper focused on the coffee business in the general aspect. For example, Usep and Mamoon examined the impact of product quality, service quality, and price on customer satisfaction within a traditional market in Indonesia (Suhud & Allan, 2019). Another study was about "Attributes of the coffee shop business related to customer satisfaction" which the author reported that the hypothesized antecedent variables were statistically significant to account for satisfaction. In particular, taste was identified as the most influential attribute accounting for satisfaction. Moreover, a significant relationship between "satisfaction" and "loyalty" was identified. (Lee & Moon, 2018) However, very few studies could hardly be found on the university area. The current study attempts to fill the gap in the literature by focusing on the investigation of the drinking coffee behavior of the consumers in the education institute and to study the coffee design as the 7Ps marketing strategies. This study may provide the new information on the aspect of coffee shop business on the campus, and give the recommendations for those who about to create the differences in doing the business in this area.

Research Objectives

1. To study the consumer's behavior of drinking coffee in the education institution
2. To study the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution

Research Methods

This study adopted a quantitative research approach for studying the behavior of drinking coffee and the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution.

Participants

The 400 participants (The 50 Administrators, the 150 staffs, and the 200 students in Burapa university) were recruited by convenience sampling from an estimated population of 50,000 (Yamane, 1967)

Instrument.

The researchers developed a questionnaire based on the previous literature. The self-administered questionnaire was used by googol form, and the main focus of the questionnaire was sought information on the opinion about the behavior of drinking coffee and the coffee shop design in the education institution. The questionnaire comprised two main parts: Thebehavior of drinking coffeeand the opinion about the coffee shop design. The final questionnaire comprised 26 items. The content validity of this survey was determined through Item – Objective Congruence (IOC) (Turner & Carlson, 2003). Furthermore, the reliability was .972 (Cronbach's Alpha Coefficient). This study received ethics approval from the Institute for Development of Human Research Protection in Thailand.

Analysis

The quantitative data was analyzed through descriptive statistics including frequency, mean, standard deviation, and with SPSS Version 21.

Results

The finding found the behavior of drinking coffee in the education institutionand the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution which can be shown in the table 1 to table 4 as follows.

Table 1: The customer's opinion in the issue of the behavior of drinking coffee

The behavior of drinking coffee	Numberof people	Average (X̄)
Brand		
Inthanin	22	5.5
Amazon	185	46.25
Doi Chang	6	1.5
Starbucks	62	15.5
McDonald's	8	2.0
Doi Tong	3	0.3
Backcanyon	6	1.5
Others	108	27.0
Menu		
Cappuccino	97	24.3
Espresso	43	10.8
Mocha	49	12.3
Latte	104	26.0
Americano	20	4.8
Others	87	21.8
The reason of the coffee shop selection		
Nearby the office	56	14.0
Nearby the house	103	25.8
The coffee quality	86	21.5
The shop's space is convenient	126	31.4

Good cake	11	2.8
Good atmosphere	18	4.5

The result from the table 1 found that Amazon was the most favorite band (185 people, $\bar{X} = 46.25$), the second most favorite band was others (108 people, $\bar{X} = 27.0$), and the least favorite band was Doi Tong (3 people, $\bar{X} = 0.3$). In the aspect of menu, the most favorite menu was Latte (104 people, $\bar{X} = 26.0$), the second most favorite menu was Cappuccino (97 people, $\bar{X} = 24.3$), and the least favorite menu was Espresso (43 people, $\bar{X} = 10.8$). In the aspect of the reason of the coffee shop selection, the best reason was to choose the coffee any shop where has convenience space (126 people, $\bar{X} = 31.4$), the second one was the nearby the house (103 people, $\bar{X} = 25.8$), and the least favorite reason of selecting the coffee shop was the good cake (11 people, $\bar{X} = 2.8$).

Table 2: The customer's opinion in the issue of designing the coffee shop as the 7Ps marketing strategy.

Opinion	Number of people	Average (\bar{X})
The most suitable color for the coffee shop		
White	30	7.5
Green	3	0.75
Orange	24	6.0
Red	25	6.25
Brown	13	3.25
Sky blue	96	24.0
Pink	163	40.75
Blue	11	2.75
Black	3	0.75
Purple	29	7.25
Others	3	0.75
The original country for selecting coffee beans		
Brunei	30	7.5
Cambodia	3	0.8
Laos	24	6.0
Malaysia	25	6.3
Philippines	13	3.3
Singapore	96	24.0
Thailand	166	41.2
Indonesia	11	2.8
Myanmar	3	0.8
Vietnam	29	7.3

The result from the table 2 found that Pink was the highest favorite color for decorating the coffee shop (163 people, $\bar{X} = 40.75$), the second highest favorite was sky blue color (96 people, $\bar{X} = 24.0$), and the least favorite were green, black, and others (3 people, $\bar{X} = 0.75$). For the issue of selecting the coffee beans from the oversea found that the most famous country was Thailand (166 people, $\bar{X} = 41.2$), the second famous country was Singapore (96 people, $\bar{X} = 24.0$), and the least famous country were Cambodia and Myanmar (3 people, $\bar{X} = 0.8$).

Table 3: The customer's opinion in the issue of designing the coffee shop as the 7Ps marketing strategy (Continuous)

Opinion	Number of people	Average (\bar{X})
Price		
46 - 50 Baht	148	37.0
51 - 55 Baht	84	21.0
56 - 60 Baht	76	19.0

61 - 65 Baht	33	8.25
66 - 70 Baht	15	3.75
71 - 75 Baht	17	4.25
76 - 80 Baht	7	1.75
81 - 85 Baht	5	1.25
86 - 90 Baht	1	0.25
91 - 95 Baht	3	0.75
More than 96 Baht	11	2.75
The needs of the national snack		
Yes	352	88.0
No	48	12.0
The service expectation		
The coffee quality and taste	154	38.5
The barista quality	33	8.25
Good taste of snake	22	5.5
Good atmosphere	111	27.75
Good service	40	10.0
ASEAN book available	10	2.5
Sufficient seats	10	2.5
Wi-Fi free available	20	5.0
Decorated by the national furniture of ASEAN countries		
Agree	348	87.0
Disagree	52	13.0

The result from the table 3 found that the highest favorite price rate was 46 - 50 Baht (148 people, $\bar{X} = 37.0$), the second highest favorite price rate was 51 - 55 Baht (84 people, $\bar{X} = 21.0$), and the least favorite rate was 81 - 85 Baht (1 person, $\bar{X} = 0.25$). Most customers need the national snack (352 people, $\bar{X} = 88.0$). The highest expectation towards the service from the customers was the coffee quality and taste (154 people, $\bar{X} = 38.5$), the second highest expectation was the good atmosphere (111 people, $\bar{X} = 27.75$), and the least expectation were ASEAN book available and Sufficient seats (10 people, $\bar{X} = 2.5$). Most customers agree that the coffee should be decorated by the national furniture of ASEAN countries (348 people, $\bar{X} = 87.0$).

Table 4: The customer's opinion in the issue of designing the coffee shop as the 7Ps marketing strategy (Continuous)

Opinion	Number of people	Average (\bar{X})
Using and serving to the customer by the national ASEAN cup, bowl, and plate		
Agree	369	92.25
Disagree	31	7.77
Using the national ASEAN uniform for the staff		
Agree	311	77.75
Disagree	89	22.25
Decorating the coffee shop by the history books of ASEAN		
Agree	381	95.25
Disagree	19	4.75
Setting the coffee shop as the place for giving the cultural knowledge of ASEAN		
Agree	384	96.0
Disagree	16	4.0
The coffee shop model is able to extend the franchise		
Agree	374	93.5

Disagree	26	6.5
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The result from the table 4 found that most customers agree with using and serving to the customer by the national ASEAN cup, bowl, and plate (369 people, $\bar{X} = 92.25$), most customers agree with using the national ASEAN uniform for the staff (311 people, $\bar{X} = 77.75$), most customers agree with decorating the coffee shop by the history books of ASEAN (381 people, $\bar{X} = 92.25$), most customers agree with setting the coffee shop as the place for giving the cultural knowledge of ASEAN (384 people, $\bar{X} = 96.0$), and the coffee shop model is able to extend the franchise (374 people, $\bar{X} = 93.5$).

Discussion

The finding of this study is consistent with the previous researches and relevant articles about studying the behavior of drinking coffee in the education institution the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution can be described that

1. To study the consumer behavior of drinking coffee in the education institution of found that Amazon was the most favorite coffee shop band which is relevant to the work of Thananporn and her research team that their title is "What drives experiential loyalty? A case study of coffee chain stores in Bangkok", and the result showed that the today market in Thailand these days is dominated by Amazon Coffee with existing outlets of over 2,123 stores nationwide(ThananpornSethjinda&WongphunLaothumthum, 2019). Their most favorite menu was Latte which relates to the finding of George Van Doorn and his research team in the title of "Latte are influences both the expected and rated value of milk-based coffee drinks" which found that the presence of latté art influences how much people expect, and are willing, to pay for a café latté. As such, adding art to, and the type of visual design on, a customer's drink should be considered by those serving café latté as an effective means of increasing value (Doorn, Dashwood, Baillie & Spence, 2015), and their most reason for selecting the coffee shop to use the service was nearby the houses which relates to the article of Susan Ward in the title of "How to start a successful coffee shop" which found that one of the best reason of setting up the coffee shop is to open the coffee shop close to the community (Ward, 2021).

2. To study the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution found that their most suitable color for the coffee shop was Pink which relates to the work of PrabuWardono and his research team in the title of "Effect of interior colors, lighting and decors on perceived sociability, emotion and behavior related to social dinning" which found that the restaurant with monochromatic colors, dim lighting and plain décors yielded a statistically significant difference in the entire dependent variables with almost any other interior conditions on romantic dining, as opposed to the case of casual dining (Wardono, Hibino & Koyama, 2010). Their most adorable coffee beans come from Thailand which relates to the work of PrachaTechanant and his research team in the title of Quality of Arabica coffee beans planted under different planting patterns by Akha tribe, Wawee sub-district, Mae Suai district, ChaingRai province which found that those coffee beans that grows in the natural forest in Thailand are higher quality than those grow in other coffee planting types (PrachaTechanant, WitchaphartSungpalee, SawikaKonsaeng&PhanitNakayan, 2017). In the issue of pricing, 46 to 50 Baht per cup would be the most acceptable price for the customers which relate to the finding from Jong-Wen Wann and his research team in title of Consumer preferences of locally grown specialty crop: The case of Taiwan coffeewhich found that the customers are not willing to pay the premium for these attributes. With regards to external quality, consumers prefer the attributes of specialty café style and product featured packaging (Wann, Kao & Yang, 2018). Most customer needs the national snack which relates to the article of McCormick in the title of "Coffee and dessert pairings", and the article said that choose the right dessert, and you've got a balanced final course that will leave everyone satisfied (McCormick, 2019). In the issue of the service expectation, the coffee quality and taste was the most concern from the customer expectation which is relevant to the work of Kim Ho-sik with the title of "The effects of service qualities on customer satisfaction and behavioral intention in coffee shop", and the result found that one of the qualify coffee shop factors should pay attention the product quality as the priority (Sik& Hyun, 2017), most customers are happy to see the coffee shop decorated by thy ASEAN furniture, ASEAN accessories for the furniture and the staff includes with the cultural and history books which relates to work of Lisa Waxman in the title of "The coffee shop: social and physical factors influencing place attachment", and the finding found the top five design considerations included: cleanliness, appealing aroma, adequate lighting, comfortable furniture, culture related to sense of belonging, territoriality and networking, sense of community, and feeling of community (Waxman, 2006), and most customers agree that this model can be extended to the franchise which relates to the work of IlanAlon in the title of "A systematic review of international franchising", and the finding found that in the international business, franchising has been studied as a mode of entry, it has also been examined in other disciplines such as management, marketing and entrepreneurship using different theoretical lenses and different variables of interest, including internationalization (Alon, Apriliyanti, Parodi, 2020).

Conclusion

This research finding found that in the issue of studying the consumer behavior of drinking coffee, Amazon was the most favorite coffee shop band, their favorite coffee menu was Latte, and most of their reason for selecting the coffee shop was nearby the house. In the issue of studying the 7Ps strategy for designing the coffee shop in the education institution found that most favorite color for designing the coffee shop was the Pink, the most favorite coffee beans came from Thailand, the most reasonable price for a cup of coffee was 45 to 50 Baht, most customers are happy to have the national snack, the most expectation from the customers was the coffee quality and the taste, most customers are happy to see the shop decorated by the ASEAN furniture, accessories for the shop and the staff, ASEAN culture & history, and they agreed that this model can be extended to the franchise.

Recommendations

There are some recommendations from this study. First, the research finding can be adapted to design the business model for being the knowledge center of coffee and the ASEAN cultural places for those students who need to practice doing the business along with learning in their class, and Second, to design the deference and the options for the consumers.

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